

Nematicidal Properties and Phytochemical Screening of *Tamarindus Indica* and *Azadirachta Indica* Extract Against Burrowing Nematode of Banana Plant in Sokoto State

Muhammad I.A.^{*1}, Aliyu L.S.², Ismaila A.³, Musa A.²

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Science, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto Nigeria

³Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: Muhammad, I.A., Tel: +234(0) 8065628145; E-mail: imranamhammad40@gmail.com

Received: September 12, 2017, Accepted: October 02, 2017, Published: October 02, 2017.

ABSTRACT:

Nematodes of banana are one of the major constraints to sustainable banana production in Sokoto and worldwide. This nematode can reduce plant growth, yield by more than 50%, and decrease the productive life of banana fields. *Radophulus similis* control in the Sokoto and Nigeria at large has been based on the application of synthetic nematicides, which are now costly and discouraging due to human health and environmental hazards. The objective of this study was to assess the nematicidal properties of neem and Tamarind Extract and to determine the phytochemical properties of these extracts. Result showed that, Alkaloids, saponins, triterpens, and steroids were found in all the extracts, tannins in the *T. indica* only. All the extracts cause a significant reduction by 27-56%. It was found that among the extracts tested, *A. indica* had maximum percentage reduction (56%), while *T. indica* extracts showed minimum percentage reduction (27%) against *R. similis* nematodes. Therefore, *A. indica* could provide farmers with a simple, low cost alternative for the control of banana nematodes. It would be appropriate for more researches should be done in order to come up with an alternative to synthetic nematicides.

Keyword: *Nematodes, Phytochemical, Banana, Tamarindus and Azadirachta indica*

INTRODUCTION

Banana (*Musa* spp.) is one of the most important crops produced in over 130 countries of the world [1]. Bananas are the fourth-ranked crop in the world and first among fruits with annual sales of about US\$2.5 billion [2]. Worldwide distribution of burrowing nematodes prevented exclusion of nematode from new banana plantations and caused the persistence of nematodes problem [3]. Studies carried out in Nigeria revealed that the most predominant nematodes affecting banana were; *Radophulus similis*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, *Helycotylenchus multicinctus*, *H. pararobustus*, and *Pratylenchus coffeae* [4]. However, [5] observed that, *R. similis* and *P. coffeae* were the most damaging of all nematodes that parasitize bananas.

Burrowing nematode, *Radophulus similis* (Tylenchida: Pratylenchidae) is the most economically important nematode that parasitize banana plant affecting its quality and quantity. There are studies on burrowing nematodes in Nigeria [6], their presence and impact on banana. It also found in Africa, Asia, Australia, North and South America and many Island regions. They infect many plants, which includes banana, pepper, and citrus. The nematode causes dark and necrotic lesions, stunting of root system, unthrifty and rotting of root system [7]. It is against this backdrop and other related to agricultural production that agrochemicals have been playing a major role in meeting yield requirements in world food production. However, much concern has arisen out of findings relating their negative impact to human health and environmental problems. Some pesticides contain active ingredients that have shown to cause loss of fertility, carcinogenesis and mutagenesis. Widespread application to most cash crops means pesticides are present in the ecosystems, aquifers and water systems of the main agricultural areas. In the long-term, this could have repercussions

for both the natural environment and human health [8].

Therefore, this study was design to assess the nematicidal activity of plant extracts on burrowing nematode, *Radophulus similis* on banana roots, to determine its impact on percentage reduction of burrowing nematodes problem for sustainable banana production in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

The plant material collected was selected and procured from field and got authenticated from an expert in the Department of Biological Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The criterion for the selection of plants was the availability of plants and previous work done on their activity.

Extract preparation

Plant materials collected were dried under shade, cleaned and ground to powdered form. The plant materials were soaked in sufficient amount of 70% aqueous-methanol by cold maceration at room temperature for a total of 3 days. After that the filtrate was collected through a piece of porous cloth and filter paper and the plant materials re-soaked twice. The combined filtrate was concentrated in a rotary evaporator at 40°C under reduced pressure to yield thick and dark colored crude extracts. These extracts were stored at -4°C until use and dissolved in distilled water on the day of the experiments to prepare stock solution and different dilutions for the purpose of evaluating phytochemical and nematicidal activity.

Extraction of Nematode

The root extraction of nematodes was prepared as described by [9]. Plant roots were gently washed, excess of water removed, cut into small pieces and then weighed. Roots were placed in a sieve

(53mm) with tissue paper and then in a glass funnel. Distilled water was slowly added and then left for 24 hours at room temperature for nematodes extraction. After 24 hours, the sieve containing roots was removed, water was collected into a measuring beaker and the volume of water was recorded. Each sample was mixed well and 2ml suspension was transferred into a counting chamber. The number of nematodes was counted and recorded.

In vitro nemacidal activity of plant Extracts

Assessment of adult mortality was done after putting the nematodes in the extract containing different concentrations (1.0, 1.5.0, 2.0 and control 0.0g) of each component for 2days by direct count of dead nematode after filtering. The oviposition was assessed by counting the number of eggs laid on a random sample of 20 nematodes. Two weeks after treatment the test tubes were examined and number of emerged offspring counted after

filtration. The same were applied to control in each treatment and replicate. Nematodes were considered dead if they did not respond to being touched by a small probe. The percentage of mortality was determined. This experiment was repeated thrice.

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0. Means were separated using the least significant difference at 5% probability level.

RESULTS

Result of phytochemical analysis showed that, Alkaloids, saponins, triterpens and steroids were found in all the extracts, tannins is present in the *A. indica* and absent in *T. indica*, while phenols is present in *T. indica* and absent in *A. indica*. The results were presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Classes of secondary metabolites recovered from neem and tamarin extracts.

Secondary metabolite class	<i>A. Indica</i>			<i>T. indica</i>		
	EOE	ME	WE	EOE	ME	WE
Alkaloids	+	+	+	+	+	+
Saponins	+	+	+	+	+	+
Triterpenoids	+	+	+	+	+	+
Steroids	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tanins	-	-	-	+	+	-
Phenol	+	-	-	-	-	-

+ Present; - absent; EOE: essential oil extract; ME: methanol extract; WE: water extract.

Table 2: Effect of the Leaf extracts on adult mortality of *Radophulus similis*

	Treatment (g) Per 20 <i>Radophulus similis</i> .							
	<i>T. indica</i>				<i>A. indica</i>			
Replications	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control
1	8	10	10	0	3	2	4	0
2	6	9	10	0	5	3	5	0
3	8	8	9	0	0	4	3	0
Total number	22	27	29	0	8	9	12	0
Percentage (%)	36.6	45.0	48.3	0	13.3	15	20	0

Table 3: Effect of the Leaf extract on eggs of *Radophulus similis*

	Treatment (g) Per 20 <i>Radophulus similis</i> .							
	<i>T. indica</i>				<i>A. indica</i>			
Replications	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control
1	10	9	5	1	20	16	19	0
2	11	5	6	0	19	18	17	0
3	13	6	6	2	19	15	15	0
Total number	34	20	17	3	58	49	51	0
Percentage (%)	56.6	33.3	28.3	5.0	96.6	81.6	85.0	0

Table 4: Effect of the Leaf extract on offspring of *Radophulus similis*

	Treatment (g) Per 20 <i>Radophulus similis</i> .							
	<i>T. indica</i>				<i>A. indica</i>			
Replications	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control	1.0	1.5	2.0	Control
1	6	4	3	0	6	6	6	0
2	5	2	0	0	8	8	8	1
3	3	3	0	2	5	5	5	3
Total number	14	9	3	2	19	19	19	4
Percentage (%)	23.3	15.0	5.0	3.3	31.7	31.7	31.7	6.6

Mortality of adult *Radophulus similis* per 20 individuals in a Petri-dish one-week post leaf extract treatment (Table 2). This shows a high rate of death when treated with *T. indica* with 36.6%, 45% and 48.3% at 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0g/20 organisms respectively; the effect of the treatment is slightly independent of the change in concentrations. *A. indica* shows a lower mortality when compared

with *T. indica* and the effect of the treatment. The effect of the extract treatment is almost insignificant compared to those of *T. indica* and *A. indica*. This effect is independent of the increase in amount of treatment used. There is no significant difference due to the treatment. The results were presented in Table 2:

Oviposition was highest in the *A. indica* leaf extract treatments

(Table 3) with 96.6, 81.6 and 85.0 eggs at 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0g/20 egg, and least is the *T. indica* leaf treatments (Table 3) which gave 56.6, 33.3, 28.3 eggs at 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0g/20 eggs, while control remain negative for *A. indica* and somehow positive for *T. indica* with 5% mortality only. The efficacy increased with an increase in the amount/weight of leaf extract used. The results were presented in table 3.

The emergence of offspring at two weeks post leaf extract treatment was highest in *A. indica* treated eggs (Table 4) which gave 31.7% of each treatment at 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0g /20 eggs respectively. Lowest values were recorded in the *T. indica* treated extract (Table 4) 23.3, 15.0 and 5.0 at 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0g/20 eggs respectively. It was also observed that the emergence number decreases with an increase in the weight of the leaf extract treatments used.

Discussion

This investigation aimed at determining the secondary metabolite composition of several neem and tamarind leaf extracts and evaluates their nematocidal properties and thus potential for control of *R. similis*. Essential oils, Methanol and water extract were tested here together with powder. The extraction processes produced similar yields for the essential oil extract as found by [10]. Phytochemical analysis of *A. indica* and *T. indica* in this study showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, triterpens and steroids which were reported to have nematocidal properties by other workers [11, 12]. Tannins was found in essential oil extract and methanolic extract of *A. indica* while phenols were only detected in the essential oil extract which is in consonance with the findings of [13] and [12] who added that tannin and phenol in the essential oil extract were known to inhibit nematodes development. Since all extracts of both *A. indica* and *T. indica* contained secondary metabolite families known to have nematocidal properties [14, 12]. This would explain positive effects of the extract tests.

The mortality rates of *R. similis* treated with *A. indica* extracts was observed to be higher mortality than those treated with extracts of *T. indica*. This could be due to the presence of phenol in *A. indica* extracts a compound, which is known to possess nematocidal effect [13, 12]. The phytochemicals found in *T. indica* demonstrated similar but less effective in killing the *R. similis*. This inconsistency may be due to the lack of phenols in *T. indica* which has nematocidal effect. This study showed the nematocidal properties of three neem extracts and tamarind powder. These three formulations significantly decreased banana root necroses and inhibited population growth of *R. similis*. Even though all three extracts showed good nematocidal properties, the neem powder seems most promising. These results are similar to findings by Musabyimana and Saxena [15] who studied the efficiency of neem seed sub-products against nematodes *Pratylenchus goodeyi* Sher and Allen and *Meloidogyne* spp. which seriously affect plantain. A higher efficiency of the neem seed powder could be explained by the fact that the powder contains all secondary metabolites present in the neem leaf while the extractions might either have limited the number and quantities of certain metabolites in the extracts [16].

Conclusions

The application of phytochemicals (azadirachtin and tamarinds) as alternatives to synthetic nematocides was found effective and comparable to ethoprophos at preventing plant growth and yield losses. This will be beneficial to banana producers by decreasing the time for fruiting and increasing the productive life of the fields. Plants treated with azadirachtin and tamarinds also had a low root necrosis index which may result in fewer plants toppling and uprooting. In the pursuit of more benign

pest management and more consumer-acceptable solutions in banana production it would be appropriate for more research to be directed to organic research of this kind that ensure safety of human lives and environmental productivity for economic and sustainable banana production in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

1. F.E, Brooks. Burrowing Nematode. The Plant Health Instructor (2008). <http://www.apsnet.org/edcenter/intropp/lessons/Nematodes/Pages/Burrowingnematode.aspx> (Viewed: 16 April, 2017).
2. R.C, Plotz Blach Sigatoka of banana. *The Health Instructor*. Online doi : 10.1094/PHI-I-2001-0126-01. Accessed 28th January, 2004.
3. S.R., Gowen, P, Quénéhervé, and R. Fogain. Nematode parasites of bananas and plantains. In: Luc, M., Sikora, R.A., Bridge, J. (Eds.), *Plant Parasitic Nematodes in Subtropical and Tropical Agriculture*. CAB International, Wallingford, UK, (2005) pp. 611-643.
4. P.R. Speijer, and D. De Waele. Nematodes associated with East African highland cooking bananas and cv. Pisang Awak (*Musa* spp.) in Central Uganda. *Nematology* (2001) 3(6): 535-541.
5. A. Elsen, and D. De Waele,. Recent development in early invitro screening for resistance against migratory endoparasitic nematodes in *Musa* spp. Katholieke universiteit Leuven, Belgium (2002)
6. O.E. Okafor., K.I. Ugwuoke., C.L. Mba., F.C. Okafor, and J.I. Mbadianya. The distribution of plant-parasitic nematodes of *Musa* spp. In Nsukka agricultural Ecological Zone, Enugu State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. (2015)10 (48) :4338-4347.
7. European and Mediterranean Plant Protection organization. *Diagnostics*. OEPP/EPP Bulletin. (2008) 38 :374-378.
8. I.A. Salau., K. Shehu., A.B. Kasarawa., S. Sambo, and A.A. Shahida. Fungi Associated with post-harvest rot of commonly consumed fruits in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Advanced Botany and Zoology* (2015) 3 (3): 1-4
9. S.K. Ibrahim, L. Ibrahim and I. Choueiry. The occurrence of burrowing nematodes on banana in Lebanon and their control using plant extract: *World Research Journal of Entomology and Nematology*. (2012)
10. J. Kumar, B.S. Parmar. Physicochemical and chemical variation in neem oils and some bio activity leads against *Spodoptera litura* F. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* (1996) 44, 2137-2143.
11. F.J. Gommers, and J. Barker. Physiological diseases induced by plant response or products. In: Poiner, G.O., Jansson, H.B. (Eds.), *Diseases of Nematodes*, (1988) vol. 1.
12. A. Faouzi. Etude sur l'utilisation des nématicides et la persistance du fenamiphoros sur la culture de tomate sous serre dans la région de sous Massa. Mémoire de fin d'étude IAV H, Agadir Maroc (2002).
13. M.A. Siddiqui, and M.M. Alam. Control of the parasitic nematode by *Tagete tenuifolia*. *Rev. Nematol* 11, 369-370. Boca Raton, CRC Press Inc., Florida, USA, (1988) pp. 3-22.
14. A. Kapil, S. Sharma, and S. Wahidulla. Leishmanicidal activity of 2 Benzoxazolinone from *Acanthus illicifolius* in vitro. *Planta Med.* (1994) 60, 187.
15. T. Musabyimana, and R.C. Saxena. Efficacy of neem seed derivatives against nematodes affecting banana. *Phytoparasitica* (1999) 27, 43-49.

16. M. Akhtar. Biological control of plant-parasitic nematodes by neem products in agricultural soil. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* (1998) 7, 219-223.

Citation: Muhammad, I.A *et al* (2017). Nematicidal Properties and Phytochemical Screening of *Tamarindus Indica* and *Azadirachta Indica* Extract Against Burrowing Nematode of Banana Plant in Sokoto State. *J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology*. V5I3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1000549

Copyright: © 2017 Muhammad, I.A, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.